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ФУНДАМЕНТАЛ ТАДҚИҚОТЛАР ЖУРНАЛИ

ЖУРНАЛ ФУНДАМЕНТАЛЬНЫХ ИССЛЕДОВАНИЙ | JOURNAL OF FUNDAMENTAL STUDIES

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EXPERIENCE OF FOREIGN COUNTRIES IN THE FIGHT AGAINST DRUG TRAFFICKING IN SEAPORTS

ANNOTATION

This article examines sea basins as routes used by drug gangs to transport drugs, as well as various ways to move such drugs and psychoactive substances by sea vessels. Simplification of customs procedures when transporting goods by sea, large accumulations of goods, accelerated loading and unloading procedures make control less strict, which attracts and activates organized crime in seaports. The activities of law enforcement agencies of foreign countries at checkpoints on the land border are also reviewed.

Keywords: narcotic drugs, psychotropic substances, sea basins, seaports, sea vessels, Russia, Afghanistan, China, the Netherlands, border control, customs control, production, transportation.

ДЕНГИЗ ПОРТЛАРИДА ГИЁҲВАНДЛИК ВОСИТАЛАРНИНГ НОҚОНУНИЙ АЙЛАНИШИГА ҚАРШИ КУРАШИШДА ХОРИЖИЙ МАМЛАКАТЛАР ТАЖРИБАСИ

АННОТАЦИЯ

Мақолада наркогуруҳлар томонидан гиёҳвандлик воситаларни денгиз ҳавзалари орқали ташиш учун фойдаланиладиган йўллар, шунингдек, гиёҳвандлик воситалари ва психотроп моддаларни денгиз кемалари орқали ташишнинг турли усуллари кўриб чиқилган. Денгиз орқали товарларни олиб ўтишда божхона тартиб-қоидаларининг соддалаштирилиши, товарларнинг катта миқдорда тўпланиши, юкланиши ва туширилишида назорат етарлик даражада амалга оширилмайди, бу эса денгиз портларида уюшган жиноятчиликни фаоллашига олиб келади. Шунингдек, мақолада хорижий давлатлар ҳуқуқни муҳофаза қилиш органларининг қуруқликдаги чегара ўтказиш пунктларидаги фаолияти ҳам кўриб чиқилган.

Калит сўзлар: гиёҳвандлик воситалари, психотроп моддалар, денгиз ҳавзалари, денгиз портлари, денгиз кемалари, Россия, Афғонистон, Хитой, Нидерландия, чегара назорати, божхона назорати, ишлаб чиқариш, ташиш.

ОПЫТ ЗАРУБЕЖНЫХ СТРАН В БОРЬБЕ С НАРКОТРАФИКОМ В МОРСКИХ ПОРТАХ

АННОТАЦИЯ

В данной статье рассмотрены морские бассейны как маршруты, используемые наркогруппировками для перевозки наркотических средств, а также различные способы перемещения таких средств и психоактивных веществ морскими судами. Упрощение таможенных процедур при перевозке товара морским транспортом, большое скопление товара, ускоренная процедура погрузки и выгрузки делают контроль менее строгим, что притягивает и активизирует организованную преступность в морских портах. Также рассмотрена деятельность правоохранительных органов зарубежных стран в пунктах пропуска на сухопутной границе.

Ключевые слова: наркотические средства, психотропные вещества, морские бассейны, морские порты, морские суда, Россия, Афганистан, Китай, Нидерланды, пограничный контроль, таможенный контроль, производство, перевозка.

Big money comes with big business, and drug trafficking is big business with international opportunities. All ongoing research classifies crimes related to drug trafficking as the most dangerous international legal problems of our time [1].

At the same time, maritime transport has unintentionally played an unfavorable role in the transport of narcotic drugs and psychoactive substances for many years.

In Russia, out of 62.3 thousand km of borders, 37.6 thousand km are on sea borders and 24.6 thousand km are on land borders [2], which predetermines close, including criminal, ties with foreign territories.

Such large-scale access of Russia to the seas and oceans provides the opportunity to establish economic ties with 127 countries of the world, and on land - only with 18 states.

The existing geopolitical position, as well as difficulties in organizing and implementing border and customs control, increase interest in Russia from international organized crime, including those associated with the international drug business.

It is necessary to note the high level of organization of drug gangs and their good technical equipment, the use of modern information and communication technologies.

One of the features of the modern drug situation is the continuation of the process of internationalization of illicit drug trafficking. The intensive expansion of the Russian market for narcotic drugs and psychoactive substances continues.

For the production of narcotic in Russia there is a significant raw material base, but technology does not stand still, as evidenced by the significant increase in the number of seized synthetic drugs.

Their share in the total mass of seized narcotic drugs and psychotropic substances has increased 13 times over the past 10 years and, at the end of 2017, ranks second after cannabis drugs (26.1%; 5.6 tons) [3].

At the same time, the share of drug trafficking resulting from drug smuggling is becoming increasingly significant. The main source of replenishment of the Russian drug market is still the smuggling of highly concentrated drugs, mainly heroin, from Afghanistan, as well as synthetic drugs from the Baltic countries, China, and the Netherlands.

The drug business includes a number of stages: production, transportation, and sales. Taking into account the fact that persons involved in drug trafficking are increasingly using the latest Internet technologies, producing components and precursors in different countries, organizing contactless sales and using other technologies to conceal their illegal activities, it can be stated that the production and Sales are the least vulnerable stages.

And as before, the biggest bottleneck is the transportation of narcotic drugs and psychotropic substances. Thus, we noted earlier that about 70% of narcotic drugs and psychotropic substances arrive in Russia from abroad, while the courier or cargo is at greatest risk when crossing state borders, which by definition are lines of increased control.

In this regard, drug criminals choose logistics routes and types of transport routes that run in places with a minimum number of checks.

Law enforcement agencies quickly responded to changes in the situation at checkpoints on the land border, which disrupted previously established smuggling schemes and forced drug groups to change existing routes, find new mechanisms for transporting drugs, using fragmentation of shipments and the use of other transport routes, including sea routes.

To do this, they often use the possibilities of multimodal transportation. Trends in the development of the drug trafficking system show the intensification of the use of maritime transport for the transport of drugs.

This is due to the following factors:

- organs;
- vastness of sea spaces;
- insignificant or complete absence of those inspecting and monitoring the technological and design features of sea vessels, making customs inspections practically impossible and ineffective;
- features of cargo movement and its volumes.

These factors facilitate smuggling and cause increased interest in this area of international transnational criminal communities, including those involved in drug trafficking.

The increased use of maritime routes in connection with the strengthening of land borders is also discussed in the United Nations Office on Drugs and Crime, where the report presented talks about the main drug routes through maritime spaces [4].

This trend is confirmed by the seizure of large quantities of narcotic drugs in European and Russian ports. Scientists from different countries have come to the conclusion that it is necessary to strengthen the fight against drug trafficking in maritime spaces [5].

To do this, they consider it necessary to amend the UN Convention against Illicit Traffic in Narcotic Drugs and Psychotropic Substances of December 20, 1988 [6], allowing a state aware of illegal activities related to illicit trafficking in narcotic drugs and psychotropic substances to accept measures against the crew of a sea vessel involved in the smuggling of narcotic drugs and psychotropic substances: "... despite the autonomy of the vessel's territory and the openness of the sea spaces..." [7].

While airports, train stations and stations are now subject to strict controls, seaports still provide ample opportunity to hide drugs inside legal goods. Simplification of customs procedures when transporting goods by sea, large accumulations of goods, accelerated loading and unloading procedures make control less strict, which attracts and activates organized crime in seaports.

Thus, foreign goods can be moved in the international transport transit mode, that is, without the intention of leaving and using them on the territory of the transit country.

For such cargo, inspection is not carried out at all, only external safety is inspected (for example, containers are inspected for the integrity of seals), which makes it possible to use the Russian Federation as a platform for the transit of cargo and cargo. For example, in the Vostochny port (Nakhodka) a container was installed that was traveling from Kazakhstan in transit to South Korea; according to the documents, it contained sewing threads. When inspecting the container, a violation of the integrity of the container seal was discovered; after opening it, 14 tons of ephedra were discovered [8].

The scale of global trade is such that customs authorities are currently unable to conduct a thorough examination of sea vessels. Taking into account the fact that Russian seaports annually increase trade turnover, the situation is predicted to become more complicated.

The international community knows examples when transit supplies of drugs, using directly the population of the transit country, influenced the security and stability of the country as a whole by putting pressure on law enforcement agencies and the political system [9].

The trends in the distribution of drugs and drugs in the Russian Federation indicate the use of the following sea areas: cocaine mainly enters Russia through the Baltic ports, opiates through the ports of the Black Sea and Caspian basins, so-called synthetic drugs through the ports of the Far Eastern sea basin.

On the borders with the Baltic countries and in the Kaliningrad region, the situation is characterized by the intensive movement of small quantities of smuggled drugs of plant and synthetic origin. There is an increase in the supply of synthetic drugs in the Baltic countries and the Kaliningrad region.

In addition, it is necessary to note the growing trend in the import of precursors used for the manufacture of NS and PP to the Baltic countries. In particular, the St. Petersburg seaport is the northern hub of drug trafficking routes, which can be used to transport large quantities of drugs into Europe hidden in shipping containers. This route is also used for transporting cocaine intended both for the Russian domestic market and for transit to European ports [10].

There has been a significant increase in drug trafficking of synthetic drugs from the People's Republic of China (hereinafter referred to as the PRC), including by sea. The main drug-dangerous destination for the supply of synthetic drugs from abroad are the cities of the PRC, where the main facilities of the Chinese chemical industry are located (Shijiazhuang, Suzhou, Jingzhou, Shanghai) [11].

A significant fact in assessing the peculiarities of the current situation is that all synthetic drugs transported across the customs border of the Customs Union are purchased via the Internet and subsequently sent from the manufacturer located in the PRC to the recipient in the Russian Federation.

It should be noted that these drug gangs responsible for movement routes consist of citizens of several countries. Drug traffickers use sea transport to smuggle hashish from the PRC to distribute it to members of fishing and fish processing vessels directly on the high seas.

A typical route for these vessels: Russia – China – Republic of Korea – Japan – Malaysia – China. The traffic pattern indicates that the crew members of the receiving transport vessels of the fishing fleet have found a way to enrich themselves without violating the legislation of the Russian Federation on combating drug trafficking, since the sale of narcotic drugs purchased in the PRC is carried out without entering Russian ports.

Taking into account the routes being carried out, the main threat to the supply of narcotic drugs to the ports of the Far Eastern sea basin is the following directions:

- from the countries of Southeast Asia (PRC, Kingdom of Thailand) to the Russian Federation; from the Russian Federation to the countries of Southeast Asia (illegal export of controlled substances intended for personal use is possible).

At present, it is not possible to estimate the volume of supplies of “Chinese drug trafficking” due to the fact that synthetic drugs are practically not supplied; precursors are supplied, already prepared and packaged for the manufacture of NS and DS at home. In addition to the Chinese direction, supplies from Turkmenistan exist and are actively developing through the Caspian port of Turkmenbashi, from which drugs are supplied to Azerbaijan and Russia.

Due to the current logistics situation, drug gangs consider ports as the only stable destination and transfer shipments disguised in goods and in sea vessels.

In the Turkmen transport system, the maritime industry occupies a significant place in ensuring export-import relations. From the port of Turkmenbashi, the most intense ship traffic is carried out to the ports of Baku and Makhachkala. Quite a significant amount of Turkmen cargo flows in transit through the territory of the Russian Federation and through the territory of Azerbaijan.

The UN Committee on Disarmament and International Security has repeatedly paid attention to Azerbaijan in its reports as the main transshipment base for Afghan drugs. For this republic, transit transportation of goods is a strategically important component of state economic policy, which is actively used by drug gangs [12].

It is characteristic that all large smuggling of narcotic drugs was organized by drug gangs, which included persons of Azerbaijani nationality who accepted Russian citizenship. The Ministry of National Security of Azerbaijan and the UN committee believe that the Russian drug mafia is largely controlled by ethnic Azerbaijanis. Similar information is contained in the world drug report, where Azerbaijan is mentioned as a transit state for heroin from the Islamic Republic of Iran.

The report talks about the following route: heroin from Iran is transported to Azerbaijan, then through the Black Sea to Ukraine, and then the route splits over land - the drugs go either to the Russian Federation or through the Republic of Moldova are delivered to Romania for further transportation along the eastern branch of the Balkan route to Western Europe [13].

This is facilitated by historically established relationships, family and ethnic ties, a special border crossing regime and joint foreign economic activity, which allowed trans-border criminal drug communities to turn all these conditions to their advantage.

To combat smuggling, you need to know how to commit these crimes, based on two main situations:

1. The captain or crew members are aware of the contraband cargo.
2. The crew of a sea vessel are unwilling smugglers.

Let's consider ways of committing crimes in the first situation. Analysis of crimes related to illicit trafficking in sea basins allows us to identify a set of methods and techniques used when committing crimes at these sites:

1.1. Delivery of NS and PV directly from the seaport. Delivery of drugs from shore to vessels (passenger, transport, fishing, research, etc.) located in the port or entering and leaving it. It is typical for a drug trafficker to hire a courier from among the crew members or passengers of a sea vessel.

The courier receives a financial reward for future or already completed work; his task is to bring drugs onto the ship, hide them, deliver them to their destination and remove them from the ship. Moreover, if a crew member acts as a courier, they have more options than a passenger. A courier from among the crew has easy access to places where it is convenient to hide drugs (holds, ballast tanks, fuel tanks, various warehouses, etc.).

1.2. Supply of narcotic drugs and psychotropic substances bypassing the seaport. Delivery of narcotic drugs and psychotropic substances to ships or their unloading outside the port, near the coast (inland waters, territorial sea) using small self-propelled and non-self-propelled vessels (structures), from small aircraft or other aircraft by dropping containers equipped with a beacon.

Subsequently, containers are lifted on board in specially designated areas or in places where the beacon was activated.

1.3. Supply of narcotic drugs and psychotropic substances through "overload". Transfer of drugs between ships away from the coast by mooring each other and passing drug shipments. The sale and transfer of narcotic drugs and psychotropic substances on the high seas occurs at the time of delivery of food products on board, as a rule, fish processing vessels and collection of finished fish products.

In cocaine-producing countries such as Colombia, Ecuador and Venezuela, container ships and fishing vessels are most often used to transport drugs. The following scheme is very often used: the ship receives cargo in neutral waters from the so-called semi-submersible vessels, which are low-slung boats up to 25 meters long, the surface part of which protrudes above the surface to a height of no more than 40 centimeters, with a crew of 2 to 4 people.

Such vessels can take on board up to 10 tons of cargo. This boat has a number of advantages: maneuverability, low landing and devices for rapid flooding, low fuel consumption.

The material of the vessel is close to the material from which the “invisible” structures are created, which makes it practically invulnerable to coast guard vessels and border guards. In the second situation, the crew becomes an unwitting participant in smuggling. Here are just a few ways to commit a crime in this case:

2.1. One of the passengers brings luggage with drugs onto the ship, hides it in a secluded place, and then goes ashore, and at the next closest port, another person enters under the guise of this passenger and takes out the “baggage” in the port he needs (the most rarely used method).

2.2. When loading products by stevedoring companies or during minor repairs by service personnel.

2.3. By placing a cargo with legal goods, inside of which narcotic drugs and psychotropic substances are hidden.

2.4. Placing narcotic drugs and psychotropic substances out of sight of the crew: outside the ship near the steering wheel or in the lower part of the ship’s hull.

2.5. Entering a ship while it is moving (usually when passing through canals at night) and placing narcotic drugs and psychotropic substances among legal cargo.

Thus knowledge of the method and routes of movement of narcotic drugs will allow law enforcement agencies to develop an algorithm of actions for the detection and identification of narcotic drugs and psychotropic substances both on ships and in seaports, and will also allow crew members to more carefully monitor the ship so as not to become victims crimes related to drug trafficking.

The conducted study of the problems of using maritime transport and the infrastructure of international ports in drug trafficking allows us to come to the following conclusions:

- intensive development of maritime transport greatly simplifies the supply of drugs;
- transmission channels are always integrated into existing or newly created transport routes, and there is a constant improvement in the methods of transporting drugs.

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ЖУРНАЛ ФУНДАМЕНТАЛЬНЫХ ИССЛЕДОВАНИЙ

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